

Effect of Playing Games Approach on the Numeracy Skills of Kindergarten Learners

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effect of a game-based approach on the numeracy skills of kindergarten learners and to assess the magnitude of this effect. It was conducted at Santa Cruz Central Elementary School, Santa Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The study involved 50 kindergarten learners, with 25 in section A as the control group and 25 in section B as the experimental group. Both sections were homogeneous in composition, with learners from both sections having identical grades. Non-random assignment of subjects included all learners from sections A and B as participants. The study utilized the new normal learning modality, a blended approach where teachers provided modules and met learners online while adhering to Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) protocols. Researchers conducted follow-up sessions online to discuss module content with learners. Findings indicated that the game-based approach positively impacted the numeracy skills of kindergarten learners and revealed differences in post-test scores between the control and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Playing Games 2. approach 3. numeracy skills

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1. Introduction

Developing numeracy skills early gives children a foundation for their learning and development. It prepares them for daily life, including general problem solving and handling money. Maths includes noticing numbers, shapes, patterns, size, time and measurement. Early math and numeracy skills are crucial for later academic success. This includes math achievement as well as other subjects such as reading (Fuson, Sarama, Clements, 2015). Several studies have shown the importance of early math (Aubrey Godfrey, 2003; Aunio et al., 2015; Clerkin Gilligan, 2018; Jordan et al., 2009). To begin with, clearly distinguishing numeracy from mathematics is useful. PIAAC defines numeracy as “ability to access, use, interpret, and communicate mathematical information and ideas, in order to engage in and manage the mathematical demands of a range of situations in adult life” (PIAAC Numeracy Expert Group, 2009, p. 6; Rampey et al., 2016, p. 2). Several studies have shown the importance of early math (Aubrey Godfrey, 2003; Aunio et al., 2015; Clerkin Gilligan, 2018; Jordan et al., 2009). The learning that takes place during early childhood creates a foundation necessary for future math concepts and possible vocations. Teachers and parents play a crucial role in supporting and teaching these early math concepts. Without a strong foundation and proper teach-

Where:

- O₁ - Pretest of the experimental group
- O₂ - Posttest of the experimental group
- O₃ - Pretest of the controlled group
- O₄ - Posttest of the controlled group
- - Non-random assignment of subjects
- X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

ing strategies and interventions, students will continue to struggle in math through elementary school. Children are naturally curious and interacting with their environment daily. Just by building with blocks, children are practicing spatial, sorting, and reasoning skills to make the best tower (Harris Petersen, 2019). They want to figure out which shapes can stack on each other to make the strongest and tallest tower and they want to know how tall it is. Math requires that type of curiosity to create stamina to figure out word problems or strive to understand why a math formula works. Math difficulties do not go away easily in elementary school as continues to create negative attitudes toward math leading to lower achievement (Clerkin Gilli-

gan, 2018). In order to best prepare students for their future, teachers and parents need to explicitly teach early math concepts to children beginning as infants. Having a language rich environment where children can learn the academic language required for math, is extremely beneficial for young children to learn math concepts (Harris Petersen, 2019). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, playing sorting on the numeracy skills affects the kindergarten learners. The researcher being a teacher in the above educational institution would like to explore another dimensions in solving the merging problem. Hence, this action research.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one

group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). In this case, the researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were an intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Santa Cruz Central Elemen-

tary School, Santa Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	25
2	Section B	25
	Total	50

were the 50 kindergarten learners – 25 were from section A which will be the controlled group and 25 were from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both

learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where teacher gave modules while meeting the learners online, adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what had been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consisted of a 25 –item test that eventually

determined the numeracy skills of the research subjects. The pre-test was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pre-test was very helpful in assessing the numeracy skills of the kindergarten learners. On the other hand, the post-test was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of numeracy skills of the kindergarten learners, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking permission for the research study to be conducted, which was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Santa Cruz Central Elementary School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the

experts of the study. After permission has been granted for the study to be conducted in Santa Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered pretest to both controlled and experimental classes and eventually commenced her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered post-test to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made an analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the level of the numeracy

skills of the learners in both pre-test and post-test scores. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of the playing games approach on the numeracy skills of the kindergarten learners

Description of Student Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed of 14.16 or Beginning while the experimental the pre-test scores of the grade kindergarten group got the mean of 15.38 or Beginning learners. The controlled group got the mean

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	25	14.16	56.64	Beginning
Experimental Group	25	15.38	61.5	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Aunio et al., (2015) and Harris Petersen (2019) that children are in the resultative counting stage and can accurately count objects by only counting each object once, begin to add and subtract small quantities and understand that the last number said when counting is the total amount. Soon after, they enter the shortened counting stage and can identify numerals and count on from any given number (Aunio et al., 2015; Harris and

Petersen, 2019). The task at the early childhood level, among many other things, is to prepare the early childhood age cohort with the guiding principles of numeracy. “Improvements will only be reflected at the higher levels of education when children receive quality education at the basic level” (Rev. Ronal Thwaites qtd. in Angus, 2016). Concerning numeracy in particular, several researchers have found evidence to support the notion that the quality of mathematical experiences in the early years is a chief contributor to subsequent individual achievement – academic and otherwise (Doig, McCrae Rowe, 2003; Perry, 2000).

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	25	20.47	81.88	Developing
Experimental Group	25	22.08	88.32	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the kindergarten learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.47 or Developing level while the experimental group gained the mean of 22.08 or Approaching Proficiency level. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-

test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.7 from a mean rating of 15.38 to 22.08. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the

idea that Children are naturally curious and interacting with their environment daily. Just by building with blocks, children are practicing spatial, sorting, and reasoning skills to make the best tower (Harris Petersen, 2019). They want to figure out which shapes can stack on each other to make the strongest and tallest tower and they want to know how tall it is. Math requires that type of curiosity to create stamina

to figure out word problems or strive to understand why a math formula works. In order to best prepare students for their future, teachers and parents need to explicitly teach early math concepts to children beginning as infants. Having a language rich environment where children can learn the academic language required for math, is extremely beneficial for young children to learn math concepts (Harris Petersen, 2019).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.44	.0361

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.44 with a p-value of .0361 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the kindergarten learners. This implies that the used of playing games approach on the numeracy skills have contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the kindergarten learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Harris Petersen, (2019) who said that in order to best prepare students for their future, teachers and parents need to

explicitly teach early math concepts to children beginning as infants. Having a language rich environment where children can learn the academic language required for math, is extremely beneficial for young children to learn math concepts (Harris Petersen, 2019). Early math and numeracy are the general understanding of numbers and basic mathematical concepts (Harris Petersen, 2019; Toll Van Luit, 2014). These are skills such as counting, comparing and contrasting, describing shapes and positions and problem solving (Aunio, Heiskari, Van Luit Vuorio, 2015; Aubrey Godfrey, 2003; Harris Petersen, 2019; Ramani Eason, 2015).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 6 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
50	-4.52	0.441	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of playing games on the numeracy skills approach By Kindergarten age, children are in the resultative counting stage and can accurately count objects by

only counting each object once, begin to add and subtract small quantities and understand that the last number said when counting is the total amount. Soon after, they enter the short-

ened counting stage and can identify numerals and count on from any given number (Aunio et al., 2015; Harris and Petersen, 2019). Children are naturally curious and interacting with their environment daily. Just by building with blocks, children are practicing spatial, sorting, and reasoning skills to make the best tower (Harris and Petersen, 2019). They want to figure out which shapes can stack on each other to make the strongest and tallest tower and they want to

know how tall it is. Math requires that type of curiosity to create stamina to figure out word problems or strive to understand why a math formula works. These relational skills are not only essential for early numeracy development, but also critical for future math learning (Aunio et al., 2015). Students will always need to be able to know how numbers are related to one another throughout their math career.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of playing games approach on the numeracy skills of kindergarten learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Hagonoy 1 District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 50 kindergarten learners – 25 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 25 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of playing games approach on the numeracy skills of kindergarten learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the kindergarten learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching kindergarten learners must have numeracy-related activities and visual-spatial activities available for children to play with. If learners take part in the learning process by experiencing the unfolding of the lesson, then he will appreciate the concept being develop, thus, he is learning. It's never too early to introduce children to concepts of numeracy; early childhood is a crucial time for brain development, so it's important to think about how you can support the children in your nursery to acquire numeracy skills. The school heads should promote the use of playing games approach on the numeracy skills as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed

in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that are narrative in nature and are not interesting to learners. A school policy about the utilization of playing games approach on the numeracy skills can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using playing games approach on the numeracy skills as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of playing games approach on the numeracy skills in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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